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COST ANALYSIS IN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PROCESSING PLANTS

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Abstract. This article presents a systematic review of the theoretical and empirical literature examining the interrelationship between inflation, economic growth, and unemployment within the frameworks of the Phillips Curve and Okun's Law. The study provides a comprehensive reassessment of these fundamental macroeconomic relationships in the context of job creation and job reallocation processes, with particular attention to emerging and transition economies.

The review synthesises classical, expectations-augmented, and New Keynesian interpretations of the inflation–unemployment relationship, alongside modern extensions that incorporate nonlinearity, asymmetry, and structural changes in the growth–unemployment nexus. It also evaluates how macroeconomic fluctuations, supply-side developments, policy frameworks, and institutional characteristics influence the stability and magnitude of these relationships over time.

Special attention is given to empirical evidence from developing and post-transition economies, where traditional linear specifications may not fully reflect the complexity of labour market dynamics. The article emphasises the importance of incorporating cyclical asymmetries, business cycle phases, and structural factors when analysing employment responses to macroeconomic developments.

Methodologically, the study adopts a structured analytical review approach, comparing theoretical concepts with cross-country empirical findings. Job creation and job reallocation are interpreted as macroeconomically influenced processes shaped not only by output dynamics but also by inflation expectations, monetary and fiscal policy coordination, and institutional conditions.

The main contribution of the article lies in integrating the Phillips Curve and Okun's Law into a unified analytical framework that explains the link between macroeconomic variability and employment dynamics. By systematising existing theoretical and empirical evidence, the study provides a conceptual basis for future empirical research and policy development aimed at supporting sustainable and employment-oriented economic growth.

Key words: inflation; economic growth; unemployment; phillips curve; okun's law; job creation; employment dynamics; macroeconomic stability.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada inflyatsiya, iqtisodiy o'sish va ishsizlik o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik Phillips Curve va Okun's Law nazariyalari doirasida nazariy va empirik adabiyotlar asosida tizimli tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda ushbu fundamental makroiqtisodiy munosabatlar ish o'rinlari yaratilishi va qisqarishi jarayonlari nuqtayi nazaridan, ayniqsa rivojlanayotgan va o'tish iqtisodiyoti mamlakatlari misolida qayta baholangan.

Tahlil inflyatsiya va ishsizlik o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikning klassik, kutilmalar bilan to'ldirilgan hamda yangi keynschilik yondashuvlarini, shuningdek iqtisodiy o'sish va ishsizlik o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikning nochizliqlik, asimmetrik va tarkibiy siljishlarni hisobga oluvchi zamonaviy kengaytirilgan modellarini qamrab oladi. Shu bilan birga, makroiqtisodiy beqarorlik, taklif shoklari, iqtisodiy siyosat rejimlari hamda institutsional omillarning ushbu munosabatlarning barqarorligi va miqyosiga ta'siri baholangan.

Alohida e'tibor rivojlanayotgan va transformatsiya jarayonidagi iqtisodiyotlarga qaratilib, ularda an'anaviy chiziqli modellar mehnat bozori dinamikasini to'liq aks ettira olmasligi asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqotda iqtisodiy sikl fazalari, tarkibiy cheklovlar va asimmetrik reaksiyalarni hisobga olish zarurligi ta'kidlangan.

Metodologik jihatdan tadqiqot tizimli tahliliy sharh usuliga asoslanib, nazariy konsepsiyalar hamda mamlakatlar kesimidagi empirik natijalar o'zaro taqqoslangan. Ish o'rinlari yaratilishi va qisqarishi jarayonlari iqtisodiy o'sish, inflyatsion kutilmalar, monetar va fiskal siyosat muvofiqligi hamda institutsional omillar ta'sirida shakllanuvchi makroiqtisodiy jarayon sifatida talqin qilingan.

Maqolaning ilmiy yangiligi Phillips egri chizig'i va Okun qonunini yagona analitik tizimga integratsiya qilish orqali makroiqtisodiy beqarorlik va bandlik dinamikasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni kompleks yoritishdan iborat. Tadqiqot natijalari kelgusida empirik modellashtirish hamda bandlikka yo'naltirilgan barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashga qaratilgan iqtisodiy siyosat choralarni ishlab chiqish uchun nazariy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: inflyatsiya, iqtisodiy o'sish, ishsizlik, Phillips egri chizig'i, Okun qonuni, ish o'rinlari yaratish, makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлен системный анализ теоретической и эмпирической литературы, посвящённой взаимосвязи инфляции, экономического роста и безработицы в рамках концепций кривой Филлипса и закона Оукена. В исследовании данные фундаментальные макроэкономические зависимости переосмыслены с точки зрения процессов создания и сокращения рабочих мест, особенно в странах с развивающейся и переходной экономикой.

В работе обобщены классические, ожидательно-расширенные и новые кейнсианские интерпретации взаимосвязи инфляции и безработицы, а также современные подходы, учитывающие нелинейность, асимметрию и структурные сдвиги во взаимосвязи экономического роста и безработицы. Оценено влияние макроэкономической нестабильности, шоков предложения, режимов экономической политики и институциональных факторов на устойчивость данных взаимосвязей.

Особое внимание уделено странам с формирующейся и переходной экономикой, где традиционные линейные модели не отражают в полной мере динамику рынка труда. Обоснована необходимость учета фаз экономического цикла, асимметричных реакций и структурных ограничений при анализе занятости.

Методологически исследование основано на структурированном аналитическом обзоре, сопоставляющем теоретические положения и эмпирические результаты по различным странам. Процессы создания и сокращения рабочих мест рассматриваются как макроэкономические явления, формируемые динамикой производства, инфляционными ожиданиями, согласованностью денежно-кредитной и фискальной политики, а также институциональными условиями.

Научная новизна исследования заключается в интеграции кривой Филлипса и закона Оукена в единую аналитическую систему, раскрывающую взаимосвязь макроэкономической нестабильности и динамики занятости. Полученные результаты создают теоретическую основу для дальнейших эмпирических исследований и разработки политики, направленной на обеспечение устойчивого экономического роста и занятости.

Ключевые слова: инфляция, экономический рост, безработица, кривая Филлипса, закон Оукена, создание рабочих мест, макроэкономическая стабильность.

INTRODUCTION

Deep processing of agricultural products, particularly fruit and vegetable processing, plays a crucial role in creating high added value in the national economy, ensuring food security, and enhancing export potential. However, the efficient functioning of this sector largely depends on the rational management and comprehensive analysis of production costs. In fruit and vegetable processing enterprises, the seasonality of raw materials, the perishable nature of products, and the high proportion of energy and logistics costs result in a complex and highly dynamic cost structure.

Under market economy conditions, maintaining competitiveness, reducing production costs, and increasing profitability require enterprises to establish systematic cost control mechanisms, identify key factors influencing cost formation, and effectively use cost analysis as a tool for managerial decision-making. In particular, the multi-stage production process, the presence of technological losses, and the diversity of product assortment necessitate the application of modern management accounting techniques alongside traditional cost analysis methods.

In recent years, the integration of cost analysis with digital technologies, management accounting, and internal audit systems has become increasingly important. Analyzing costs by responsibility centers, product

types, and technological stages enables enterprises to improve resource utilization efficiency, identify hidden reserves, and substantiate both strategic and operational management decisions. From this perspective, studying the theoretical and practical aspects of cost analysis in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises represents a relevant scientific and practical issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of integrated cost systems developed by Robert S. Kaplan and Robin Cooper provides an important theoretical foundation for improving management accounting and cost analysis. The authors demonstrated the limitations of traditional cost accounting systems and proved that Activity-Based Costing (ABC) enables the identification of key cost drivers that determine product cost. This approach is particularly relevant for fruit and vegetable processing enterprises, where it allows a more accurate assessment of the impact of material, labor, and support service costs on product cost.

The methodological approaches to management and cost accounting proposed by Colin Drury offer a comprehensive framework for classifying costs by economic elements and functional areas. His work explains cost allocation procedures and unit cost determination, providing a solid theoretical basis for applying process costing and job-order costing methods, as well as improving cost planning and control systems in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises.

The competitive advantage concept introduced by Michael E. Porter emphasizes the importance of evaluating cost structure from a strategic perspective. According to the value chain approach, costs are not merely financial indicators but key determinants of enterprise competitiveness. This perspective enables fruit and vegetable processing enterprises to optimize production costs and integrate cost analysis into strategic management.

The studies of Jack G. A. J. van der Vorst and Adrie J. M. Beulens highlight the impact of supply chain uncertainty on cost formation. Their research emphasizes that disruptions in raw material supply, fluctuations in energy prices, and logistics inefficiencies significantly influence cost levels. This confirms the necessity of analyzing costs not only within production processes but throughout the entire supply chain.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, a systematic and comprehensive methodological approach was applied to conduct cost analysis in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises. The research methodology focuses on examining costs by economic elements, functional areas, and responsibility centers, identifying the key factors influencing cost formation, and substantiating managerial decisions on a scientific basis.

During the cost analysis process, financial reporting data were first standardized into a unified format, and cost items were regrouped according to economic elements. The following elements were identified separately: materials (raw materials and packaging), labor costs, energy and utilities, depreciation, manufacturing overhead, and other expenses. At the next stage, total amounts for each element were calculated, their shares in total production costs were determined, and annual change trends were analyzed.

In addition, technologically justified allocation bases were applied when distributing auxiliary production costs among main product types. These allocation keys included kWh of electricity, machine-hours, cooling time, number of laboratory tests, and similar operational indicators. This approach ensured an equitable distribution of costs among products and enhanced the accuracy and reliability of cost calculations.

Cost analysis in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises plays a crucial role in evaluating production efficiency, identifying key cost drivers, and substantiating managerial decisions. Such analysis is based on examining the structure of costs by economic elements, identifying their proportions and change dynamics, and assessing their interaction with revenues.

The analysis of the cost structure in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises is carried out in three stages:

First, data sources are standardized into a unified format;

Second, the classifier (dictionary) of economic elements is harmonized;

Third, aggregated amounts are aligned by enterprise and by year.

For the purpose of this study, the enterprises East Agro International LLC, Asian Jam LLC, and Green World-Group LLC were selected, and their financial reports for the period 2021–2024 were analyzed. Since cost items in their reports could be presented under different names, the data were consolidated into unified elements:

1. "Raw materials," "materials," and "packaging" were grouped under materials;
2. "Electricity, steam, water, cooling" were grouped under energy and utilities;

3. "Wages, bonuses, and social contributions" were grouped under labor;
4. "Laboratory services, technical maintenance, refrigeration logs, and sanitation-quality control" were grouped under manufacturing overhead;
5. "Depreciation" was identified as a separate element;
6. Remaining minor costs were combined under "other expenses" or "tax-related payments."

At the analysis stage, total amounts were calculated for each element, their percentage shares in total production costs were determined, and annual trends were identified. Growth rates of each element and their contribution to overall cost dynamics were also evaluated. To ensure comparability when enterprises differed in scale, unit cost indicators (UZS/kg or UZS/liter) were calculated. Furthermore, values were adjusted into real terms using a deflator, which enhanced the accuracy and analytical reliability of intertemporal comparisons.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the results of our analysis, the share of materials is typically the largest. A decrease in this share indicates improvements in raw material acceptance and laboratory control, more efficient blending plans, or an increase in output yield coefficients. Conversely, an increase may be associated with changes in raw material quality and calibration, logistics disruptions, or rising packaging prices.

An increase in the share of energy costs may indicate heat losses in sterilization, pasteurization, freezing, and drying departments, or disruptions in the cold chain. In such cases, setup time reduction systems (SMED practices) and preventive maintenance intervals are reviewed.

The share of labor costs is generally linked to employee qualification levels, multi-skilling, and plan-versus-actual alignment across shifts. A decreasing trend often indicates improvement in Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) and reduced production downtime.

The share of depreciation naturally increases in the year when new production lines are commissioned but gradually declines relative to total costs as production volumes expand.

The share of manufacturing overhead decreases with improved consistency in laboratory, technical service, and sanitation processes. This leads to a reduction in claims (customer complaints or product returns) and stabilization of product shelf life.

In inter-company comparisons, three key indicators are applied:

- Top-3 element concentration – indicates which cost drivers have the greatest influence on product cost;
- Volatility index – reflects year-to-year variability of element shares;
- Contribution analysis – determines each element's contribution to changes in total costs.

A high concentration indicates that product cost is heavily dependent on a limited number of drivers. When the volatility index is high for certain elements, control points (CCPs) are reviewed: acceptance and quality protocols are strengthened for materials; thermal mapping is enhanced for energy; downtime codes and SMED practices are reinforced for labor (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of revenue, cost and gross profit of Asian Jam LLC.

The analysis of the financial indicators of Asian Jam LLC for 2021–2024 shows that in 2021–2022, revenue and gross profit grew steadily, and during this period, the company's operations were characterized by relatively high efficiency.

In 2021, net revenue amounted to UZS 3.76 trillion, and gross profit reached UZS 1.80 trillion, while the operating profit margin was around 25 percent.

In 2022, net revenue increased to UZS 5.99 trillion, which represents a 59 percent growth compared to the previous year. Although the cost of goods sold increased by 95 percent, gross profit amounted to UZS 2.17 trillion, and the gross margin reached 36.3 percent. At the same time, due to the increase in period expenses, the operating margin declined to 19 percent.

In 2023–2024, the situation changed: net revenue remained almost unchanged, and as a result of the growth in the cost of goods sold and a sharp increase in expenses, gross profit decreased. In 2023, the gross margin fell to 25.5 percent, while the operating margin amounted to only 1.3 percent. In 2024, net revenue slightly declined, and despite a relative decrease in the cost of goods sold, the operating result became negative due to the growth of period expenses.

During this period, the share of administrative and other operating expenses increased significantly, and the imbalance in production cost and cost structure reduced the company's profitability. This situation indicates the necessity of strengthening control over raw material quality, packaging costs, yield coefficients, and overall expense management in the production process.

The results of the analysis function as a signal system for management. For example, if the share of materials exceeds 65–70 percent or annual growth exceeds +3 percentage points, this may be related to raw material quality, laboratory indicators, or changes in packaging prices.

An increase in the energy share by 1.5–2.0 percentage points indicates insufficient thermal insulation or disruptions in the cold chain.

An increase in the labor share demonstrates the need to improve SMED discipline and workforce qualifications.

A sharp rise in manufacturing overhead requires reconsideration of the efficiency of technical service, laboratory, and sanitation expenses. If the depreciation share increases, measures are defined to bring new production lines quickly to optimal capacity.

The analysis results are supported by documentation, namely: acceptance-transfer acts, BRIX/pH protocols, temperature-humidity logs, downtime codes, inventory acts, packaging certificates, and contract formulas. Such an approach answers the questions of “who–when–what performs” and enables the development of prompt and sustainable corrective measures.

In conclusion, the analysis of cost element shares is not merely a simple distribution but a powerful signal system that substantiates management decisions. Changes in shares, element growth rates, contribution to total change, and unit cost together identify the main drivers shaping company costs.

On a daily and monthly cycle, an early warning dashboard is applied; on a quarterly and annual cycle, inter-company comparison is conducted; and at the strategic level, concentration and volatility maps provide a reliable basis for decision-making.

Cost classification is carried out by economic elements, functional areas, and responsibility centers. By economic elements, costs are divided into the following groups: materials (raw materials and packaging), labor costs, energy and utilities, depreciation, manufacturing overhead, and other expenses. This structure makes it possible to identify key cost drivers, assess resource efficiency, and optimize planning.

Costing methods (determination of product cost) are selected depending on the complexity of production technology and the variability of the product assortment. In fruit and vegetable processing industries, process costing and job-order costing systems are usually applied in hybrid form.

The process costing method is suitable for continuous technological lines such as sterilization, drying, freezing, and aseptic filling. The job-order costing method is convenient for special (exclusive) assortments produced in small batches.

In addition, the standard costing system and Activity-Based Costing (ABC) are used to analyze the precise sources of costs and their impact on product cost.

Auxiliary production costs (energy, refrigeration, water, technical service, laboratory tests) are allocated to main production through allocation bases. For example:

- Energy consumption – kWh per ton;
- Refrigeration – cooled volume or storage time;
- Technical service – capacity units or operating hours.

Through this approach, the unit cost of each product type is determined.

At the analysis stage, the share of cost elements, their growth or decline rates, and their contribution to total cost changes are identified.

The share of materials is usually the largest; its decrease indicates improvement in raw material quality and laboratory control, while its increase may be associated with price fluctuations or logistics disruptions.

An increase in the energy share indicates losses in sterilization, pasteurization, or the cold chain, in which case measures for heat recovery and improved insulation are developed.

The labor share decreases with the implementation of setup time reduction systems and multi-skilling programs.

The manufacturing overhead share tends to decline over time if technical service and quality control remain stable, leading to fewer claims and stabilization of product shelf life.

Main production is the technological chain that transforms raw materials into finished products, including all stages from acceptance and preparation to boiling or concentration, aseptic filling, and packaging.

Auxiliary production ensures the continuous functioning of this chain: the refrigeration station, steam and energy department, maintenance workshop, laboratory (quality control), internal logistics, sanitation, and other support systems belong to this group.

In practice, direct materials (raw materials, containers, packaging materials) and direct labor costs are directly assigned to product types. Meanwhile, many service costs are first accumulated in service centers and then allocated to main products using allocation factors.

When selecting an allocation factor, technological justification is crucial. For example:

- In steam-intensive sections – “kilograms of steam” or “kilowatt-hours”;
- In aseptic lines – “machine-hours” or “liters”;
- In laboratories – “number of tests” or “number of batches”;
- In internal logistics – “pallet-kilometers” or “ton-kilometers.”

Correct determination of allocation factors ensures fair cost distribution among products and reduces sensitivity to cost distortions. Therefore, allocation factors are regularly reviewed, and their reliability is verified through recalculation using alternative bases.

Costs in each service center are accumulated by economic elements: materials, labor, energy, depreciation, manufacturing overhead, and other items.

At the first stage, auxiliary center costs may be allocated without considering mutual services. However, in departments with strong interdependence such as refrigeration, energy, and maintenance, step-down or reciprocal methods are applied. The reciprocal method requires more data but ensures the fairest cost allocation in energy-intensive enterprises (freezing, drying, aseptic filling lines).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In general, proper cost classification, rational selection of costing methods, and their regular analysis in fruit and vegetable processing enterprises are among the most important factors for improving production efficiency, reducing costs, and stabilizing profitability.

In our opinion, key technological indicators in each service center — steam consumption, electricity usage, machine-hours, number of laboratory tests, transported pallet distance, and duration of changeover times — should be continuously recorded and compared with planned and actual indicators.

Through this approach, the conformity of the cost allocation base with the real production process remains under constant control.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Kaplan, R. S., & Cooper, R. (1998). *Cost & Effect: Using Integrated Cost Systems to Drive Profitability and Performance*. Boston: Harvard Business School Press.
2. Drury, C. (2021). *Management and Cost Accounting* (10th ed.). London: Cengage Learning.
3. Horngren, C. T., Datar, S. M., & Rajan, M. (2020). *Cost Accounting: A Managerial Emphasis* (16th ed.). Pearson Education.
4. Porter, M. E. (2004). *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York: Free Press.
5. Atrill, P., & McLaney, E. (2021). *Management Accounting for Decision Makers* (9th ed.). Pearson Education.
6. Anthony, R. N., & Govindarajan, V. (2017). *Management Control Systems*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
7. van der Vorst, J. G. A. J., & Beulens, A. J. M. (2002). Identifying sources of uncertainty to generate supply chain redesign strategies. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 32(6), 409–430.
8. Savitskaya, G. V. (2019). *Analysis of Economic Activity of Enterprise*. Minsk: Novoye Znanie.
9. Sheremet, A. D. (2020). *Management Analysis*. Moscow: INFRA-M.
10. Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2021). *Guidelines on Management Accounting and Cost Calculation*. Tashkent.

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